

Non-Gaussian regression models with correlated errors

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Abstract

We introduce regression models with non-Gaussian and serially correlated errors and propose an estimation method for the models. We incorporate an additional parameter into the regression models in order to induce normality and then, simultaneously estimate all the parameters. To this end we explore a posterior estimation method on the wavelet domain. Performances are assessed using a simulation study.

Key Words: Non-Gaussian, Posterior estimation, Regression, Serially Correlated, Wavelet Transform

1. Introduction

We consider linear regression models with non-Gaussian and serially correlated errors and propose a power transformation method for those models so that the transformed models satisfy approximate Gaussian condition. We here consider long memory processes for serially correlated errors though the proposed method works for other correlated errors. It is based on a wavelet-based Bayesian estimation method using the Box-Cox power transformation in order to simultaneously estimate all the model parameters under the assumption that the transformation parameter is *unknown*. Since the unknown long memory parameter together with the unknown transformation parameter greatly complicates the estimation procedure due to the dense variance-covariance of long memory processes, we simplify the estimation procedure through wavelet transform to dependent and independent variables of the models. Although we do not prefer any specific estimation method, a posterior estimation method using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) is adopted for estimations of the model parameters on wavelet domain. Our method combines existing tools, such as discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and collapsed Gibbs sampler, in a novel manner to produce estimates of the transformation parameter and other regression parameters.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we introduce discrete wavelet transforms. The Box-Cox regression model and its likelihood functions on the time and wavelet domains are presented in Section 3. A Bayesian computation procedure for model parameters and simulation study are given in Section 4 and 5, respectively.

2. Discrete Wavelet Transform

Wavelets have a strong connection to long memory processes. They have ability to simultaneously localize such processes in the time and scale domains, resulting in representing many dense matrices in a sparse form. When transforming measurements from a long memory process, wavelet coefficients are approximately uncorrelated, in contrast with the dense long memory covariance structure of the data, see Tewfik and Kim (1992). For discrete wavelet transforms, size of data n is usually assumed as a power of two, but this is not a real restriction and methods exist to overcome the limitation allowing wavelet transforms to be applied to any length of data (Taswell and McGill, 1994). For example, a zero-padding method or a truncation method are commonly used in wavelet literature. For

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sake of simplicity, we assume $n = 2^J$ and J is a positive integer denoting the scale of the data in this paper.

3. Long memory regression models

We consider and present a wavelet-based Bayesian estimation procedure of the Box-Cox long memory regression models with fractional Gaussian noise (fGn) errors. Suppose that $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)'$ is observed with covariates $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{x}_0, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{p-1})$ where $\mathbf{x}_0 = (1, \dots, 1)'$ and $\mathbf{x}_k = (x_{1k}, \dots, x_{nk})'$, $k = 1, \dots, p-1$, and that \mathbf{y} follows a non-Gaussian long memory process with an unknown long memory parameter. Through the Box-Cox transformation of \mathbf{y} ,

$$\mathbf{y}_\lambda = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{y}^\lambda - 1}{\lambda}, & \text{for } \lambda \neq 0 \\ \log(\mathbf{y}), & \text{for } \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1a)$$

$$(1b)$$

we assume that the transformed data \mathbf{y}_λ approximately follow a Gaussian long memory process (Ko, 2010). We then consider the following Gaussian regression model with long memory errors,

$$\mathbf{y}_\lambda = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_0, \dots, \beta_{p-1})$ is a $(p \times 1)$ vector of regression parameters and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is a $(p \times 1)$ vector of approximate Gaussian long memory error. We assume that the transformation parameter λ is unknown but varies over $(-3, 3)$, which is a range frequently used by practitioners. Our goal here is to develop a simultaneous estimation method for the unknowns: the transformation λ such that \mathbf{y}_λ follows an approximate Gaussian distribution, the regression parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, the long memory parameter H of fractional Gaussian noise (fGn) error, and the innovation variance σ^2 .

Let $\Theta_H = (\lambda, \boldsymbol{\beta}, H, \sigma^2)$ be the unknown parameters in fGn error models. The likelihood function related to the transformed series \mathbf{y}_λ is

$$L(\Theta_H) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-n/2} |\Sigma_H|^{-1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{(\mathbf{y}_\lambda - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})' \Sigma_H^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_\lambda - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})}{2\sigma^2} \right] J(\lambda, \mathbf{y}),$$

where $J(\lambda, \mathbf{y}) = \prod_{i=1}^n y_i^{\lambda-1}$ is the Jacobian due to the Box-Cox transformation. The variance-covariance matrix Σ_H is generated by the covariance function of fractional Gaussian noise process and very dense due to the nature of long memory processes. After applying a DWT to the model (1), the resulting transformed model is written by

$$\mathbf{y}_w = \mathbf{X}_w \boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_w,$$

where \mathbf{y}_w and \mathbf{X}_w denote the discrete wavelet transforms of \mathbf{y}_λ and \mathbf{X} , respectively. The corresponding likelihood function in wavelet domain is written by

$$L(\Theta_H) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-n/2} |\Sigma_{H_w}|^{-1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{(\mathbf{y}_w - \mathbf{X}_w \boldsymbol{\beta})' \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_w - \mathbf{X}_w \boldsymbol{\beta})}{2\sigma^2} \right] J(\lambda, \mathbf{y}),$$

where Σ_{H_w} is the $(n \times n)$ diagonalized variance-covariance matrix through DWT. Note that all the wavelet coefficients in a scale have the same variance. It is also worthwhile to know that the Jacobian $J(\lambda, \mathbf{y})$ is still evaluated on the original response data \mathbf{y} .

4. Bayesian Computation

A posterior estimation via Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) is performed in order to simultaneously estimate the model parameters Θ_H . For the prior distributions of β , σ^2 , H , and λ , we use

$$\begin{aligned}\pi(\beta, \sigma^2) &\propto \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \\ \pi(H) &\sim \text{Beta}(\eta, \nu) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\eta + \nu)}{\Gamma(\eta)\Gamma(\nu)} H^{\eta-1}(1-H)^{\nu-1} \\ \pi(\lambda) &\sim \text{Uniform}(-3, 3).\end{aligned}$$

Assuming independence among the prior distributions, the posterior distribution of Θ_H is

$$\begin{aligned}f(\Theta_H | \mathbf{y}_w) &\propto \sigma^{-n+2} |\Sigma_{H_w}|^{-1/2} H^{\eta-1} (1-H)^{\nu-1} \\ &\times \exp \left[-\frac{(\mathbf{y}_w - \mathbf{X}_w \beta)' \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_w - \mathbf{X}_w \beta)}{2\sigma^2} \right] \\ &\times J(\lambda, \mathbf{y}).\end{aligned}$$

For applying a Gibbs sampler in MCMC, full conditional distributions are needed for the unknown parameters. Let $\mathbf{X}_* = \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1/2} \mathbf{X}_w$ and $\mathbf{y}_* = \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1/2} \mathbf{y}_w$ where $\Sigma_{H_w}^{-1} = \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1/2} \Sigma_{H_w}^{-1/2}$. Then the full conditional distributions of β and σ^2 are

$$f(\beta | H, \sigma^2, \lambda) \sim N((\mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{X}_*)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{y}_*, \sigma^2 (\mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{X}_*)^{-1}) \quad (2)$$

and

$$f(\sigma^2 | H, \beta, \lambda) \sim IG\left(\frac{n}{2}, \frac{(\mathbf{y}_* - \mathbf{X}_* \beta)' (\mathbf{y}_* - \mathbf{X}_* \beta)}{2}\right), \quad (3)$$

where ‘ $IG(a, b)$ ’ denotes the inverse gamma distribution. The full conditional distributions of λ and H are, respectively,

$$f(\lambda | H) \propto (b^*)^{-a^*} \prod_{i=1}^n y_i^{\lambda-1} \quad (4)$$

and

$$f(H | \lambda) \propto D_H (b^*)^{-a^*} H^{\eta-1} (1-H)^{\nu-1}, \quad (5)$$

where $a^* = (n-p)/2$, $b^* = (\mathbf{y}_*' \mathbf{y}_* - A' \mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{X}_* A)/2$, $A = (\mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{X}_*)^{-1} \mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{y}_*$, and $D_H = |\Sigma_{H_w}|^{-1/2} |\mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{X}_*|^{-1/2}$.

Metropolis algorithms within a collapsed Gibbs sampler are performed with the full conditional distributions (2), (3), (4), and (5).

5. Simulation study

We assess the proposed method with a simple regression model with fGn errors, $\mathbf{y}_\lambda = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \mathbf{x} + \varepsilon$. Fractional Gaussian noise errors are generated with the Hurst parameter H set to 0.6, 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9 and with the innovation variance $\sigma^2 = 1$. The covariate \mathbf{x} is generated from the normal distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation 5. We set β_0 to

Table 1: Biases and Mean Squared Errors (in parenthesis)

H		$\lambda = -1.5$	$\lambda = 0$	$\lambda = 1.5$
0.6	$\hat{\beta}_0$	0.353(4.518)	0.007(0.211)	0.299(2.993)
	$\hat{\beta}_1$	0.062(0.170)	0.003(0.015)	0.069(0.115)
	\hat{H}	-0.017(0.003)	-0.009(0.002)	-0.002(0.001)
	$\hat{\lambda}$	0.016(0.004)	-0.000(0.000)	0.004(0.002)
	$\hat{\sigma}^2$	0.005(0.099)	0.021(0.012)	0.074(0.068)
	0.7	$\hat{\beta}_0$	0.294(2.726)	0.039(0.181)
$\hat{\beta}_1$		0.058(0.105)	0.024(0.013)	0.054(0.098)
\hat{H}		-0.002(0.002)	-0.004(0.001)	-0.001(0.002)
$\hat{\lambda}$		0.014(0.002)	-0.001(0.000)	0.003(0.002)
$\hat{\sigma}^2$		0.027(0.064)	0.033(0.020)	0.119(0.082)
0.8		$\hat{\beta}_0$	0.230(1.919)	0.057(0.266)
	$\hat{\beta}_1$	0.027(0.070)	0.026(0.008)	0.105(0.110)
	\hat{H}	-0.018(0.002)	-0.014(0.002)	-0.014(0.001)
	$\hat{\lambda}$	0.008(0.002)	-0.000(0.000)	0.010(0.002)
	$\hat{\sigma}^2$	0.019(0.066)	-0.000(0.000)	0.112(0.094)
	0.9	$\hat{\beta}_0$	0.351(1.175)	0.066(0.399)
$\hat{\beta}_1$		0.040(0.045)	0.016(0.005)	0.029(0.052)
\hat{H}		-0.031(0.002)	-0.032(0.002)	-0.015(0.003)
$\hat{\lambda}$		0.008(0.001)	-0.000(0.000)	0.002(0.001)
$\hat{\sigma}^2$		-0.080(0.077)	-0.048(0.086)	-0.099(0.074)

-20 and 20, and β_1 to -3 and 3. Finally, the non-Gaussian long memory response data \mathbf{y} are generated by $[\lambda(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \varepsilon) + 1]^{1/\lambda}$ with $\lambda = -1.5, 0, 1.5$. Daubechies minimum phase wavelet with 4 vanishing moments is adopted for discrete wavelet transform, and sample size is fixed to 256.

Table 1 summarizes the biases and mean squared errors of the parameter estimates $\hat{\beta}_0$, $\hat{\beta}_1$, \hat{H} , $\hat{\lambda}$ and $\hat{\sigma}^2$. The biases and MSEs of $\hat{\beta}_0$ and $\hat{\beta}_1$ appear to increase as $|\lambda|$ increases. It is known that the biases and MSEs of the regression parameters $\hat{\beta}_0$ and $\hat{\beta}_1$ deteriorate as λ increases in the numerical examples of the Box-Cox regression models with independently and identically distributed errors by Spitzer (1978). We conjecture that this phenomenon is due to the long range dependent feature of the errors. The biases and MSEs of the parameter estimates are relatively small when λ equals zero.

6. Concluding remarks

We propose a wavelet-based Bayesian approach for a simultaneous estimation of the Box-Cox regression models with long memory errors under the assumption that the long memory and transformation parameters are unknown. Although we adopt fGn processes as a serially correlated errors in this paper, the proposed estimation method is quite general and flexible, and so is easily applicable to other correlated errors.

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